

A framework for collaboratively monitoring nature and the environment

A tool to integrate the contribution that wider society can make to the science, survey and assessment of nature and the environment

UK Centre for
Ecology & Hydrology

NCEA | Natural Capital
and Ecosystem
Assessment

This first draft framework describes why we need to monitor nature and the environment, what specific things we can most usefully monitor and how wider society can support and contribute to this monitoring (for example as citizen scientists).

We focus here on the urban environment, but the underlying structure can be applied to other ecosystems.

The framework describes:

- the shared interest in the condition of our urban environments as beneficial ecosystems
- how we can monitor the natural resources and functions of these beneficial ecosystems (the natural capital approach)
- the potential for more people to take part in urban ecosystem science, survey and assessment.

What is this framework aiming to achieve?

The framework helps communities design, communicate, and carry out the scientific monitoring needed to advance our collective understanding of the state and value of nature and the environment, (in this instance, within urban spaces). The framework helps identify opportune areas to focus, coordinate and collaborate public and private investment in science, survey and assessment. Equally it empowers local communities to both participate and take informed action for local nature.

The framework aims to help:

- Increase coordination and communication between local and national stakeholders who sponsor, enable or otherwise participate in professional or volunteer environmental monitoring
- Share learning and tools between local stakeholders and natural capital professionals for more strategic deployment of monitoring capability

- Combine efforts to maximise our collective capacity to achieve a more complete picture of the state and value of nature and the environment
- Identify and address emerging survey needs, challenges and priorities
- Promote closer community coordination and more collaborative survey effort
- Improve data reliability, sharing and use.

How can you contribute to the framework development?

This is an initial draft of the framework, framed against the needs and interests of urban environments. We expect both the underlying framework and ecosystems covered to evolve to help advance and better reflect the needs of participatory science stakeholders.

If you would like to contribute to future development or have any feedback, please contact:
participatory.science@naturalengland.org.uk

A key to the framework

This initial framework was developed in consultation with Natural Capital and Ecosystem Assessment (NCEA) partners and wider stakeholders that benefit from, sponsor, enable or otherwise participate in nature and environmental survey.

The framework brings together the natural capital perspective at national scale (B, C, D) with the local stakeholder and participatory science perspective (E, F, G) under a shared goal for the urban environment (A).

Sections B, C and D describe the 'what' and 'why' of the national or natural capital approach to urban nature and environmental monitoring.

Sections E, F and G describe the local stakeholder and participatory science approach to nature and environmental monitoring. This part of the framework is about the 'who', 'why' and 'how' of local urban monitoring.

Ask yourself...

Where do you fit into the framework, at the local or national level of urban monitoring?

Key terms

Natural Capital

An economic concept which recognises that nature provides benefits and value to people (both directly and indirectly) and aims to quantify that value.

Participatory Science

Also 'citizen science' and 'community science'. This is when communities and members of the public are supported to participate in the scientific process through project design, data collection and/or analysis of findings.

Urban Environment

For this Framework, any built-up area where people live, work and play including cities, towns, villages and suburbs.

The framework

Continues on next page

The framework

E Participatory science tools and approaches

F The goals of the local stakeholders

G The local stakeholders

<p>Facilitators Initiate, create and deliver</p>	Museums	Nature organisations	Educators	Researchers
<p>Participants Organise, engage and take part</p>	The general public	Students and children	Community groups	
	Businesses	Charities	Landowners	
<p>Interested parties Support and use outputs</p>	Local council	Local service providers e.g. water, waste	Health practitioners	
	Policymakers	Records centres	Funders	

Context

This framework focuses on the urban environment. The urban environment is a complex ecosystem with highly fragmented habitats and elements of nature dispersed throughout a human-dominated landscape. Urban nature is often found in smaller areas such as gardens that are not publicly accessible. This makes it challenging to monitor. On the other hand, there is a great opportunity: many people live and work in the urban environment, creating huge potential for participatory science approaches and empowering local people to take informed action for their local urban nature.

This framework is a starting point for understanding the bigger picture. It can be used by anyone interested in monitoring the urban environment using participatory approaches. It is a living document that will undergo continued development with stakeholders and relevant experts.

B

The national and natural capital components of the framework were built in consultation with NCEA experts and partners. They reflect the goals, approaches and needs for urban monitoring using a natural capital approach.

C

Many different types of data are required. Together, and synergistically, they contribute to the measures and ultimately determine the natural capital value of urban nature. This enables us to track the state of the urban environment, to find evidence of drivers of change, and to inform high-level decision-making.

D

If you are involved in high-level natural capital approaches, this framework may be a useful tool for identifying where participatory approaches and relevant stakeholders (**E F G**) can be supported to contribute to the national picture.

E

The local stakeholder and participatory science components of the framework were built in consultation with a range of stakeholders and participatory science experts. There are many people already involved in participatory approaches to environmental monitoring in urban areas and many interested parties that could contribute. This part of the framework represents the diversity of stakeholders, their goals and the approaches they may take (or already be taking) to monitor urban nature and the environment.

F

If you are a local stakeholder, involved or interested in participatory science approaches to local monitoring, this framework may be a useful tool for planning and coordinating projects, and understanding how your outputs can align with and contribute to national scale activities: **B C D**

G

Details of the framework

A Shared goal

Healthier, climate-resilient and nature-rich towns and cities, for the benefit of people and nature

Natural capital and participatory science approaches contribute to this overarching goal and vision for a better future.

B Natural capital goal

To evaluate natural capital in the urban environment, measuring the impacts of pressures and interventions, and change through time

The Natural Capital approach is focused on evaluating the benefits that nature and the environment provides to people and communities. The goal is to quantify and measure the many facets of urban natural capital through time.

C Natural capital measures of the urban environment

The Natural Capital approach uses several measures in combination to quantify the benefits of nature and the environment. First, recording the natural assets that are present including their quantity, location and quality. Second, the Ecosystem Services or benefits to society. Third, the direct benefits of nature and the environment to people who experience and interact with it.

D The data required

Many types of data are required to build the measures of natural capital. Some of the data is already being effectively collected through participatory science, such as the significant contribution that volunteer records of species observation make to biodiversity data. Other data present opportunities for participatory approaches, such as health, wellbeing and nature connection. Other data are more challenging. For example, data on ecosystem services require scientific tools or measurements to be made, but new technologies and combinations of approaches could address these challenges.

Ask yourself...

What aspect of nature and the environment are you interested in and where does this fit into the to the national level National Capital approach?

Details of the framework

E Participatory science tools and approaches

Participatory science approaches involve local stakeholders in monitoring nature and the environment. Approaches exist on a spectrum of unstructured record collecting (e.g. ad hoc species observations through iRecord or iNaturalist) through to structured monitoring often involving specialist equipment and specific methods (e.g. the UK Pollinator Monitoring Scheme 1km square survey). Unstructured approaches are simple, little prior knowledge is required and recording can take place anytime, anywhere, so are good for mass participation. Structured monitoring requires more investment so will not be suitable for everyone, though methods can be tailored for groups of participants. Unstructured approaches favour quantity over quality of records, whereas structured monitoring can yield more detailed and robust data.

Supporting structures

There are many existing projects that you can join. NCEA is supporting the creation of a library of tools to help you find and share projects, design methods and provide guidance on data flows.

F The goals of the local stakeholders

All stakeholders will have their own unique set of motivations. However, the key goals can be broadly mapped as those that focus on assessing local nature and the environment (with data gathering being the key output) and those that focus on education, engagement and social approaches (with benefits to people being the key output). These goals are not mutually exclusive and often several goals are met within a single approach. Mapping your goals, and the goals of relevant stakeholders is a critical step in planning a participatory approach.

National Indicators

Monitoring through professional surveys and citizen science is vital for building indicators that track the state of the environment.

G The local stakeholders

There are many people and organisations already involved in monitoring nature and the environment, and many who may be interested in getting involved. The framework demonstrates the diversity of stakeholders and their different roles. Consider who else may be interested in your approach or data and communicate with them.

Choosing and using citizen science

For detailed guidance see the [guide¹](#) produced by UKCEH.

Ask yourself...

What is your goal(s) and the goal(s) of the people you are working with?

How can these be met through your approach?

1 https://www.ceh.ac.uk/sites/default/files/sepa_choosingandusingcitizenscience_interactive_4web_final_amended-blue1.pdf

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Stay in touch

If you have any feedback on this framework or would like to contribute to future work on this urban framework of those for other domains, please contact:

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UK Centre for
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<https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/natural-capital-and-ecosystem-assessment-programme/natural-capital-and-ecosystem-assessment-programme>